

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

Scientific-theoretical recommendations for identifying gifted children and introducing innovative ideas

Nasirova Gulnoza Fakhridin kizi

I graduated from UzDJTU in 2021.

From September 2021, an English teacher at Beshbola max 51 school, Jomboy district, Samarkand region

ABSTRACT In today's era of globalization, the methods of teaching young people to think creatively and analyze with unconventional methods, and to interest them in science and innovation, are highlighted in this article. Also, a number of adopted regulatory legal documents related to youth science and innovation are reflected. Even in today's advanced science and technology era, doing science remains a laborious task like digging a well with a needle.

Key words: science, renaissance, creative, youth, civil society, technology, innovative activity, legal document, international, time

Today, supporting young people, who are the largest part of the world's population, protecting them from foreign ideas and threats is an urgent issue on the agenda. Greater involvement of the future generation in science and innovation is one of the important trends of modern development. Therefore, it is true that youth issues have risen to the level of state policy. The First Renaissance in the 9th-12th centuries, the Second Renaissance in the 14th-15th centuries, i.e. the successors of our great ancestors who made their incomparable contributions to the universal civilization in the land of Uzbekistan, which is striving for a higher stage in the period of its new historical development, the Third Renaissance - young people is

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

in the eyes. Even in today's advanced science and technology era, doing science remains a laborious task like digging a well with a needle. Therefore, in the era of globalization, where competition has increased and demands for scientific innovations have increased, special attention is being paid to supporting scientific and innovative activities in our country, creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for talented young people to achieve significant results in prestigious, national and international Olympiads, competitions, contests. In this regard, training young people from traditional thinking to creative analysis, changing their attitude to science and innovation, adapting to the requirements of the times, and supporting young scientists is one of the most important main directions of the development of Uzbekistan. .

It is necessary to apply non-traditional methods of attracting young people to science and innovation in the life and education system of society.

For example, ensuring the integration between science and production, if it means combining theory with practice, introducing modern technologies in the teaching of sciences in all educational institutions, creating platforms aimed at supporting young people's start-up projects, future owners increases his enthusiasm and increases his interest in science. Increasing the scientific potential of scientific institutions and organizations, cooperation with prestigious foreign scientific organizations, wider implementation of the exchange of young scientists and scientific researchers shows that we are boldly moving towards the Third Renaissance. At first glance, the actions taken are important, but it is still too early to say about the results. There are also some weaknesses in the way that the

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

privileges established by the law reach their destination, and in the rational use of the opportunities created for young people. So there are still enough problems. Finding a solution to the problem, the role of youth in the further development of science in the country is invaluable. With nearly 20 million young people, Uzbekistan is about to lay the foundation stone of a new renaissance with such a large and new generation. "In general, the concept of the Renaissance was first used in science by Italian humanists. But it is true that hearing this word from the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, he especially admires his courage and strength and assigns responsibility to the youth. The strategic efforts under the leadership of the head of our state are motivating everyone who is not indifferent to the development of our society to become the foundation of the Third Renaissance. After all, waking up a sleepy society and people is not a prelude to AWAKENING - RENAISSANCE! Isn't it a sad result that there is no need to prove that today's Uzbekistan is not yesterday's Uzbekistan, today's youth is not yesterday's youth. Several dozen new higher education institutions have been established in Uzbekistan in recent years. Also, another new system was introduced from the 2020-2021 academic year: in order to expand the access to education of our girls growing up in low-income families, 940 additional places were allocated for them in higher education institutions on the basis of a state grant. In the current academic year, these numbers are expected to double. These changes are an important foundation for realizing the aspirations of talents, increasing their social activity, and taking a worthy place in life! Today, the development of any field in the world is impossible without innovative ideas and scientific achievements. In this sense, it is no exaggeration to say that our hard-

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

working, dedicated scientists are God-given people. They cannot be equated with others. Such people are born one out of a thousand, one out of a million, we should take care of them and support them in every way. Today, we are on the path of innovative development aimed at the radical renewal of all spheres of state and public life. It's not for nothing, of course. 1 In the new period of our national development, forming a new worldview in our people, especially uniting young people around the idea of national progress, arming them with scientific achievements and digital technologies, serves as a program-ul-action in forming a strong civil society. Indeed, quality education is the foundation of any visionary plan. It was not for nothing that the ancient Chinese thinker Confucius said: "If your plan is for one year, plant rice, if it is for ten years, plant trees, and if it is for a hundred years, educate your children." Wide opportunities are already being created in Uzbekistan to collect the expected "harvest" in the future, a system is being formed aimed at encouraging young people to study and valuing knowledge holders.

In turn, young people should be able to find sources of motivation for their personal development - be it a book or a movie, sports or travel. The entire nation should be responsible for expanding the ranks of our young men and women, who do not say that they will study when given an opportunity, but who say that they will try to acquire knowledge and develop in any situation. Many young people probably don't know that Europe was still in a heedless sleep when the Renaissance began in this holy land where we live. Perhaps there are those who do not know that this historical fact was recognized by the mature scientists of Europe. In any case, the concept of "Muslim Renaissance" by the famous German

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

orientalist Adam Mes and "Oriental Renaissance" by academician Nicholas Konrad did not fall from the sky. If we consider the book "Die Renaissance des Islams" as the main source on this topic, can we not be proud that a great scientist like Adam Mesdek relied on the scientific legacy of our great compatriot Beruni in creating a fundamental research! Hundreds of scholars such as Ibn Sina, Musa al-Khorazmi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, who matured at the famous Ma'mun Academy, contributed to the first stage of the Eastern Renaissance, and scholars such as Mirza Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, the bright representatives of the civilization of the Timurid period, contributed to the second stage of the rise. What wonder if representatives of the renaissance grow up among the children of New Uzbekistan, who have enjoyed the fruits of today's reforms! "says Alisher Sadullayev, director of the Youth Affairs Agency of Uzbekistan. 2 Necessary conditions are being created to realize the creative, intellectual and entrepreneurial potential of young people, to introduce innovative projects and modern technologies into production, to stimulate the innovative activities of talented students, young scientists and entrepreneurs. Uzbekistan's inclusion in the Global Innovation Index after a long break is one of the main and at the same time important changes for us. This can certainly be recognized as the result of the reforms carried out in our republic, in particular, the policy of transparency and openness, as well as positive changes in innovative activities.

References:

1. "From national revival to national rise", Youth Publishing House Tashkent-2019, page 55.
2. Shukhrat Satorov, "We will win", "Knowledge and intellectual potential"

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

publishing house, 2018

3. Can sadullaev-youths-have-a-third-renaissance-drivers-child

4. President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev from his speech on May 28 at the meeting dedicated to the implementation of the tasks set for the development of science and higher education.

5. Presidential decree No. PF-6097 "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030".

